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Compensatory oncogene activation during homeobox intervention.

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We describe compensatory oncogene activation during interventions involving homeobox inhibition. Whereas inhibition of PAX8 by depletion resulted in loss or silencing of *DEK*, demonstrating *DEK* silencing was a primary or proximal consequence of homeobox inhibition, compensatory oncogene activation in this setting was manifested by activation of either *ETS2* or *MN1*.